

THE JEWISH QUESTION AND THE GERMAN REFUGEES AND IMMIGRANTS IN ITALY BETWEEN THE 1930s AND THE 1940s – some numbers, a geographical distribution and the main occupations

The Italian Fascism and the Jewish question: a brief overview

From the earliest years, the political theory of the new fascist phenomenon was inspired by characters of open aggression, violence against opposition and the restoration of a past heritage represented by the myth of the Roman Empire: both in political-military terms, with the creation of a new Italian empire, and in social terms, with the foundation of a new civilisation, to consider better than others. «È destino che il Mediterraneo torni nostro. È destino che Roma torni ad essere la città direttrice della civiltà in tutto l'Occidente [...]»¹ was something that Mussolini had already showed as fundamental in 1921. With this, the racist connotations of this new political orientation were already clear and evident: the new Italian civilisation had to present itself as superior to other peoples. The totalitarianisation of the nation and the completion of the fascist revolution, in a long term perspective which has been stopped by the outbreak of the Second World War, would have gone to transform Italy and the Italians, also on a social level, into a new, regenerated country and people. Italians were to become a new race of conquerors and rulers same as the ancient Romans. Social duty, patriotism, civicism, a taste for arms and militarism, as well as harsher and more extreme characters such as racism and anti-Semitism were to be instilled in them.

In the end this was not the case: the Italians would never become Roman, because all these aspects had been imposed by cold manipulation of the regime and above all through force, coercion and propaganda. The social revolution would never be completed in Italy because not all Italians would become completely and definitively racist or anti-Semitic. It had been an imposition from above, which, although it had ideas and intentions that had started from afar, were never explicitly and expressively stated until the late 1930s, dictated above all by the rapprochement with Nazi Germany and the entry into the war, passing through also the invasion of Ethiopia in 1935-36 and the promulgation of the racial laws in 1938.²

However, before better understanding the various stages that brought fascism closer to being openly and explicitly racist and anti-Semitic, it is perhaps good to recall very briefly the organisational, cultural/ideological and institutional dimension of the fascist regime as it developed during the so-called “*Ventennio*” (the 20 years).

Organisational dimension:

Fascism was an interclass mass movement, founded on a party-militia identified in comradeship, the feeling of fraternity and the will to regenerate the nation through war and violence. The pre-existing (monarchical/democratic) state is obliterated and demobilised through both the use of violence and brutal methods, as well as through compromise and parliamentary action: the goal is the creation of a new state with a single party in power.

Cultural/ideological dimension:

Fascist culture and ideology are seen in unison as the very way of life, based on mythical thinking, the irrational, the secularism of the region of the state, national palingenesis, the heroic conception of man capable of providing for his own and the nation's destiny through violence and battle. Furthermore, fascism defines itself as 'anti', rejecting almost all the values of previous systems, born of the French Revolution: anti-materialist, anti-individualist, anti-democratic, anti-traditionalist (in the sense of the previous Italian liberal tradition), anti-capitalist, anti-Marxist. The state is in continuous, permanent revolution and fascism has a procedural character, the individual no longer

1 Cit. from a Mussolini' speech quoted in E. Gentile, *Fascismo di Pietra*, Laterza, Bari-Roma, 2007, p. 48.

2 This major topic is deeply inquired in the works of the Italian historian Emilio Gentile: specifically in *Fascismo. Storia e interpretazione*, Laterza, Bari-Roma, 2002 and in *Fascismo di Pietra*.

has private but community needs, he is totally subordinated to the needs of the state. Individuals who do not fit this conception are considered enemies of the state, to whom contempt is directed to the point of promoting persecutory measures against them: they can be political dissidents, religious, ethnic, sexual minorities, etc., but not necessarily. Fascist racism is primarily a political-spiritual concept and not a biological one, founded on the pseudo-scientific theories of eugenics, as in Nazism.

Institutional dimension:

In fascism, the central role is assumed by the *Fascist Party* (PNF) and it gradually expands its weight in power to the detriment of the monarchy, the army, the church – “*fascistation*” of the state. The head of the country, party and government is the Duce, supreme arbiter of power clashes between state and party. He is manager, military chief, symbol, leader, enabling the perfect symbiosis between party and state. An important role is played by the secret police (OVRA) with the task of preventing, controlling and repressing dissent both political and spiritual opposition to fascism. In addition, fascism organises corporately the economy with a strong emphasis on state interventionism in agricultural and industrial production and a relative decrease in private and entrepreneurial autonomy. In foreign policy, fascism champions expansionist and imperialist ideals based on the myth of the Roman Empire, the quest for international power and the emergence of a new civilisation superior to others.³

The Jewish population in Italy already organized itself in a good number of communities scattered throughout the country at the beginning of the 20th century, satisfactorily linked to the Italian social tissue. Historic Jewish communities on the peninsula were those of Livorno, Florence, Venice, Milan, Turin, Trieste (to be remembered: Italian only since 1918) and above all the largest: Rome with approximately 15,000 citizens of Jewish origin and religion.⁴ Satisfactorily linked to the Italian social tissue meant that some Jewish citizens could even hold positions of discreet prestige, especially in political and military roles. To mention just a few names, Alessandro Fortis and Luigi Luzzatti, both prime ministers in two different terms in the decade before the outbreak of the First World War, and then Sidney Sonnino – of Protestant religion but son of a Jewish father – should certainly be mentioned, Minister of Foreign Affairs in the five-year period 1914-1919, responsible for the conclusion of the *London Pact* with the *Entente* nations and Italian delegate to the *Versailles peace conference* in 1919, and Emanuele Pugliese, one of the most decorated generals of the *Regio Esercito* during the war.⁵

Fascism, despite its changeable and procedural character and since its advent in March 1919, always proved generally tolerant of the presence of Jews not only within society but also in political roles within the party and the future government: militiamen, ministers, senior army officers. Not only that, many of Mussolini's collaborators were of Jewish origin: to give just one example Margherita Sarfatti, the Duce's secret lover and author of his first biography entitled *DUX*, published in 1925 and translated into several languages as an international propaganda tool, was of Jewish origins. It is difficult to give definite numbers, but according to the research of the American historian William Brustein, between the 27th and 30th of October 1922, for the preparations and the actual *March on Rome*, some 230 militiamen – out of a total of almost 16,000 gathered from all over Italy – were of Jewish origin, a number of sympathisers destined inexorably to grow in the following years, when, against a population of about 50,000 Jews in the peninsula, it was recorded

3 E. Gentile, *Fascismo*, section “I quadri di un’interpretazione”.

4 For an overall perspective of the Italian Jewish communities in the 30s look at the map in M. Sarfatti, *Gli ebrei nell’Italia fascista. Vicende, identità, persecuzione*, Einaudi, Torino, 2000, p. 135. It can be found also at the link: <http://www.storiaxxisecolo.it/deportazione/deportazioneebrei1.htm>.

5 Tidy and concise concerning this topic is the article M. Avagliano, *Ebrei e fascismo, storia della persecuzione*, in *Patria Indipendente*, n. 6/7, June-July 2002, which will be used other times in this work.

that as many as 10,000 of them – 20% of the total – had joined the PNF (Fascist Party) before 1938.⁶

In addition to the numbers and the actual friendships the party and the regime has with people connected to the Jewish world, it is also the speeches and actions of the government that demonstrate this substantial tolerance. In one of the issues of the fascist daily newspaper *Popolo d'Italia* in 1920 Mussolini declared:

«[...] in Italia non si fa assolutamente nessuna differenza fra ebrei e non ebrei, in tutti i campi, dalla religione, alla politica, alle armi, all'economia. Abbiamo avuto al Governo persino tre ebrei in una volta. La nuova Sionne, gli ebrei l'hanno qui, in questa nostra adorabile terra, che, del resto, molti di essi hanno difeso eroicamente col sangue. Speriamo che gli ebrei italiani continueranno ad essere abbastanza intelligenti, per non suscitare l'antisemitismo nell'unico paese dove non c'è mai stato.»⁷

A position maintained even a few years later, imprinted in an official government statement:

«S.E. [Sua Eminenza] ha dichiarato formalmente che il governo e il fascismo italiano non hanno mai inteso di fare e non fanno una politica antisemita, e che anzi deplora che si voglia sfruttare dai partiti antisemiti esteri ai loro fini il fascino che il fascismo esercita nel mondo.»⁸

Again, in 1930, a year after the *Lateran Pacts*, other important manoeuvres were taken by the regime in religious matters. For the Jewish question, the most important was certainly the *Falco Law*, which united the various Jewish communities on the peninsula, creating the *Union of Italian Jewish Communities* (*Unione delle comunità ebraiche italiane*), which was well received by the population concerned – an institution that survived the fall of the regime, like many others, and which still unites the communities of Jewish faith throughout the country.⁹ Subsequently, some of the Duce's thoughts are exemplary about the issue, collected in *Colloqui con Mussolini*, published by *Hoepli* in 1932 and edited by a Jewish journalist, Emil Ludwig:

«Razza: questo è un sentimento, non una realtà; il 95% è sentimento. Io non crederò che si possa provare che biologicamente una razza sia più o meno pura [...]. Quelli che proclamano nobile la razza germanica sono per combinazione tutti non germanici: De Gobineau francese, Chamberlain inglese, Woltmann israelita, Laponge nuovamente francese. Una cosa simile da noi non succederà mai. L'orgoglio nazionale non ha bisogno di deliri di razza [...]. L'antisemitismo non esiste in Italia. [...] Gli ebrei italiani si sono sempre comportati bene come cittadini, e come soldati si sono battuti coraggiosamente.»¹⁰

However, this did not mean that in Italian political and parliamentary life there were no pockets of resistance, even from the Jewish community. Many Jewish politicians before 1922 opposed the advent of fascism, always with political and ideological rather than religious positions: they were mostly democrats, socialists or militants of the young *Italian Communist Party* (PCI), founded in Livorno in 1921.

Moreover, the same fascism and the same ideological/intellectual thought that sprung from it could not but be the offspring and filler of that great pot of ideas that had been circulating in almost

6 Cfr. W. I. Brustein, *Roots of Hate: Anti-Semitism in Europe Before the Holocaust*, Cam. University Press, Cambridge, 2003, pp. 325-327.

7 Cit. from *Tribune Juive*, 1st October 1920.

8 Cit. from the *Official Document of the Italian Government after the proclamation of Angelo Sacerdoti as the Rabbi of the city of Rome*, November 1923.

9 Concerning the topic: https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Unione_delle_comunit%C3%A0_ebraiche_italiane (IT), https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Union_of_Italian_Jewish_Communities (EN).

10 Cit. from E. Ludwig (ed.), *Colloqui con Mussolini*, Mondadori, Verona, 1950, pp. 71-72.

all European states since the last decades of the XIX century, between the *Dreyfus affair* and the more irrational currents of socialism through the influence of a minor work by the young Marx, *On the Jewish Question (Zur Judenfrage, 1843)*, overrated and notoriously misunderstood – Mussolini himself was a member of the *Italian Socialist Party* before the First World War. A mix of racist and anti-Semitic ideas was growing in a Europe, that of the second half of the XIX and early XX century, characterised by a strong resurgence of hatred towards Jews, which would later culminate in a second and much more tragic moment in the *Shoah*.¹¹

Although in the first decade of the regime Mussolini put aside anti-Semitic rhetoric and policy, he was ready to dust it off and exalt it as soon as he realised the opportunities it offered. The two-year period 1933-1934 – which corresponded to the rise to power of Adolf Hitler's *National Socialist Party (NSDAP)* in Germany – is in fact a foreshadowing of what was to come later, in the second half of the 1930s: in conjunction with the rise to power of Nazism and with the rise of an increasingly fierce imperialist policy, many newspapers loyal to the regime began to publish articles with clear anti-Semitic signals and stances intended to slowly make Jews into social outcasts.

The situation, however, was decidedly ambiguous, and remained so at least until 1938, in what is called by many historians “*the double-track policy*” (“*politica del doppio binario*”).¹² In fact, no legislative and social decisions were taken on the Jewish question: anti-Semitism became only a political instrument to get closer to Hitler's increasingly powerful Germany; for example, one of the highest fascist hierarchs, Galeazzo Ciano, ordered many Jewish officials at the *Farnesina* (Italian Ministry of Foreign Affairs) to stop dealing with their German counterparts, in compliance with the internal German policies of the time. But substantially the situation did not change too much compared to the previous years; on the contrary, the Fascist government always showed itself to be very attentive and cordial in its treatment of the Jewish population, not only Italian. Not only: for purely political and military reasons, the Italian government, due to the war in Ethiopia, also came into contact with about 30,000 Abyssinian *Falascia*, an African community of the Jewish religion that had lived in absolute isolation for centuries – Mussolini favoured this group more because they too were in opposition to the government of the Ethiopian *Negus* Hailé Selassié.

It was precisely the war in Ethiopia, however, that began to raise questions of racism and the superiority of the Italian race over all others, particularly of course over the African race. Imperialist thrust, continuous social revolution, expansionist wills in the Mediterranean under the fascist aegis and in the sign of the New Empire of Rome that had mythically risen from the so-called “*Fatal Hills*” after the conquest of the last independent kingdom of Africa, were just some of the basic motivations for this sudden and extreme change of course accompanied by the rapprochement with Germany. A rapprochement already sanctioned in the economic and political fields with the *Berlin Accords (Rome-Berlin Axis)* of 1936 and then evidently ready to expand into other, further sectors. This expansion was sanctioned by Hitler's visit to Rome in May 1938, followed a month later by that of a delegation of German experts on racism and racial eugenics. Evidence of a direct connection between the Führer's visit and the Regime's racist turn is historically unfounded, as well as historiographically untraceable; moreover, it would be unfair to shift the responsibility of Italy and Fascism for the enactment of the Race Laws and against the Jewish population onto Germany influence alone. Hitler had resolutely refrained from open interference in Italian political and social affairs in the period in question: a conclusion reached not only by De Felice but also by other historians such as Meir Michaelis as early as the 1960s, and which is now a generally accepted

11 Cfr. R. Finzi, *Il pregiudizio. Ebrei e questione ebraica in Marx, Lombroso, Croce*, Bompiani, Milano, 2011, p. 44.

12 First of them one of the most known Italian historians of the Fascist topic: Renzo De Felice. Concerning the Jewish Question: R. De Felice, *Storia degli Ebrei italiani sotto il Fascismo*, Einaudi, Milano, 1961. the work is one of the first Italian studies on the Fascist regime's policy towards the Jews, as well as a pioneering historiographical investigation on Fascism itself and the author's first contemporary history publication. It was commissioned by the *Union of Italian Jewish Communities* in 1960.

belief throughout the academic world.¹³ Yet within a couple of months of Hitler's arrival in Rome, the Italian government undertook to definitively enact racial legislation. This choice, according to many historians such as De Felice and Gentile, is to be traced first and foremost to the procedural nature of fascism as it moved ever closer to full totalitarian manifestation: explicit racism and anti-Semitism would have come out into the open at some point in history anyway. Moreover, by this time Italian-German relations had reached a point where the Fascist government was almost obliged to take decisions on racial matters: the divergence in policy on the Jewish question took too much credibility away from the two *Axis* powers, while Mussolini wanted to maintain that credibility, which represented the actual success of a *Third Way* in relation to western democratic capitalism and eastern Soviet communism.¹⁴ A certainly interesting thesis that therefore explains how, although Hitler did not explicitly ask Mussolini for racial legislation, in the end Fascism nevertheless implemented it: obviously and undoubtedly with its own margins of originality. A proof of that can be seen, to use a valid example, from a speech by Mussolini in Trieste in September of the same year, in which he responded to the criticism of those who insinuated that Fascism had blindly followed the Nazis in the racist and anti-Semitic question:

«Coloro i quali fanno credere che noi abbiamo obbedito a imitazioni, o peggio a suggestioni, sono dei poveri deficienti, ai quali non sappiamo se dirigere il nostro disprezzo o la nostra pietà. Il problema razziale non è scoppiato all'improvviso, come pensano coloro i quali sono abituati ai bruschi risvegli perché sono abituati ai lunghi sonni poltroni [...] Il problema ebraico non è dunque che un aspetto di questo fenomeno. La nostra posizione è stata determinata da questi incontestabili dati di fatto: l'ebraismo mondiale è stato, durante sedici anni, malgrado la nostra politica, un nemico irconciliabile del fascismo.»¹⁵

But the fact remains: German interference in Italian domestic and foreign affairs cannot and should not be put on the back burner. The existence of Jewish communities within the Italian social tissue and the very presence of Jews in high positions in the Fascist government represented a huge obstacle to the continuation of the collaboration between Italy and Germany, whose main political basis rested on anti-Semitism. Indeed, it is not surprising that after the capitulation on the 8th of September 1943 and the creation of the *Italian Social Republic* (RSI), it was the Germans who took the Jewish question under control, adopting all the measures of the *Final Solution* also on Italian soil. Although hypocritical and disingenuous, a certain philosemitism and tolerant attitude of Fascism towards the Jewish population in Italy could have continued, had Hitler not come to power in Germany and had there not been an economic-political-military alliance with it on the part of Italy.¹⁶ Mussolini himself in a letter of 1938 seems rather sincere in laying the “blame” for the racist turn to reasons of state, political reasons: «Circa il problema ebreo, io penso ancora una volta: non esiste! La razza? Mi fa ridere. Ma ci sono della ragioni di stato alle quali debbo ubbidire.»¹⁷

The first official document testifying to the change of course on the subject is certainly *The Manifesto of Race* (*Il Manifesto della Razza*), published in July 1938 and followed by a long series of libellous and defamatory articles against the Jews, so as to prepare public opinion for what was to

13 Analyses discussed in R. De Felice, *Storia degli Ebrei italiani sotto il Fascismo*; M. Michaelis, *Mussolini e la questione ebraica. Le relazioni italo tedesche e la politica razziale in Italia*, Edizioni di Comunità, Milano, 1982 and from the same author the more recent *Idem, L'influenza di Hitler sulla svolta razzista adottata da Mussolini*, in *La rassegna mensile di Israel*, III, vol. 69, n. 1, January-April 2003, pp. 257-266.

14 Cfr. R. De Felice, *Storia degli Ebrei italiani sotto il Fascismo*, p. 315; E. Gentile, *Fascismo*, section “*Interpretazioni del Fascismo*”; M. Michaelis, *L'influenza di Hitler sulla svolta razzista adottata da Mussolini*, p. 258.

15 Cit. from *Mussolini's speech in Trieste*, 18th September 1938.

16 Cfr. M. Michaelis, *L'influenza di Hitler sulla svolta razzista adottata da Mussolini*, pp. 263-266.

17 Cit. from *Letter to Conte Alessandro Casati*, 1938 in *L'Espresso*, 5th of July 1959, p. 13.

come in the following months. In the *Manifesto* questions were raised about the biological concept of race, about whether the Italian race belonged to the Aryan race, and of course about the Italian people's decision to declare themselves frankly and officially racist towards the peoples of the eastern Mediterranean, Africa and the Jewish population: all of whom were framed as non-European races and contaminators of pure Aryan values.¹⁸

From the 18th September – with the Mussolini' speech in Trieste – until the 17th of November of the same year, with a series of decrees-laws of various kinds, real anti-Semitic legislation was initiated: all Italian Jews are banned from public life, with restrictions on jobs, working hours, pensions and study (including university professorships), even schools are precluded to Jewish children; restrictions are placed on marriages and a family tree is used to analyse who can be considered Jewish or of the Italian race, applying exclusions only to war veterans, Fascist Party militants and other special cases; foreign Jews are precluded from setting up residence in Italy and in the territories of the Colonial Empire, and those who had settled there after the date of 1 January 1919 are granted a maximum of six months to leave these territories.¹⁹

The racial policy was supposed to continue with the expulsion of all Jews from the peninsula, starting with foreign Jews and ending with the complete expulsion of Italian Jews within ten years, although Italy's entry into the war on the 10th of June 1940 blocked the implementation of these decisions. With the conflict in progress, however, Fascism worsened the persecution by interning (in the so called “*confino*” or simply in prison) Italian Jews considered dangerous to the regime and foreign Jews whose countries had an anti-Jewish policy; moreover, concentration camps were opened in every part of Italy: from 1942, Israelites aged between 18 and 55 were conscripted into forced labour services.

The situation worsens considerably after the Armistice of the 8th of September 1943.

For the Jewish refugees in southern Italy, the persecution was over and the newly formed Badoglio government at the request of the Allies (Art. 31 of the Armistice) proclaimed that all Italian laws involving discrimination on the basis of race, colour, faith or political opinion would be repealed: this from the 24th of November 1943.

In the German-occupied centre-north, however, the situation was tragic. As early as the 23rd of September 1943, the *Reich Security Main Office* (RSHA), the central German police body that managed anti-Jewish policy, announced that Jews of Italian citizenship became immediately subject to the “measures” in force for other European Jews. The first *SS* raking, and one of the most famous, was on the 16th of October 1943 in Rome: 1259 Jews were rounded up; two days later, 1023 of them were deported to Auschwitz. The *Italian Social Republic* itself, *de facto* controlled by Germany, aggravated the circumstances. *The Charter of Verona* of the 14th November 1943 – the political manifesto of the *Republic* – resolves the problem of Italian Jews in chapter seven, stating that all members of the Jewish race are “foreigners and part of an enemy nation”. *Police Order n. 5*, issued on the 30th of November 1943 and broadcast the following day on the radio, announces that all Jews are to be sent to concentration camps, with the exception of those who are seriously ill or over seventy years of age. On the 15th of March 1944, Mussolini took a further step: he set up a *Race Office*, subordinate to the Prime Minister's Office, and placed at its head the super-racist Giovanni Preziosi, who openly claimed that the main task entrusted by Germany to the *Republic* was to eliminate the Jewish danger. One of the main sorting centres for the detention and transport of Italian Jewish citizens to the German concentration camps was the *Risiera di San Sabba* in Trieste. According to official estimates in Northern Italy, controlled by the Germans and the so-called republicans, there were about 43,000 Jews: those deported between 1943 and 1945 numbered

18 To have a much more detailed presentation of the topics in *The Manifesto of Race*:

<http://www.storiaxisecolo.it/fascismo/fascismorazz1.htm>.

19 To understand better: https://web.archive.org/web/20070521220922/http://www.anpi.it/documenti/ebrei_stranieri_espulsi.htm; <http://www.storiaxisecolo.it/fascismo/fascismorazz2.htm>; <http://www.storiaxisecolo.it/fascismo/fascismorazz5.htm>.

about 7,500, of whom only 610 survived. To the deported dead must be added the Jews killed in various places in the country, estimated at between 200 and 400.²⁰ According to Michele Sarfatti's estimates, the persecuted who were not deported or killed in Italy numbered about 35,000: compared to the other countries occupied or allied with Germany, the percentage of Jews who survived was much higher (over 80% of the total population), probably due to the fact that in Italy first the racial laws and then the Nazi persecution began several years late. Moreover, because many hundreds of Jews found refuge in Switzerland, through the Alpine passes – for example *Val Codera* –, in monasteries, in parishes – in Rome alone the Church helped more than 4,000 Jewish refugees: one example is the *Church of San Gioacchino* –, and in southern Italy. Some of them lived in hiding in the countryside, others like Primo Levi actively participated in the Resistance (many framed as partisans).²¹

20 Numbers given by G. Carocci, *Storia degli ebrei in Italia*, p. 100 and followings; official estimate given by the *Judisches Museum Berlin* and the *Memorial to the Murdered Jews of Europe's* exhibition.

21 Cfr. M. Sarfatti, *Gli ebrei nell'Italia fascista*. To expand the researches: concerning Val Codera: https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aquile_randagie#L'attivita%27_di_OSCAR; concerning San Gioacchino in Rome: https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chiesa_di_San_Gioacchino_in_Prati and all the info showed in the *German Resistance Memorial Center (Gedensktätte Deutscher Widerstand)*'s exhibition.

Introductory observation on the Jewish population in Italy before 1933

Before start discussing about the Jewish population in Italy, including both Italian citizens and foreign citizens, in the 30s and specifically from 1933 – after the rise to power of Hitler and National Socialism in Germany – it is certainly useful to take a look at the Jewish population in the peninsula in the historical period immediately previous.

As stated in many studies and also above in this contribution, the Italian Jewish population has always enjoyed relative peace within the country since its unification in 1861. Unlike other European states such as Germany or France, in Italy there were never any major episodes of anti-Semitism and in general this phenomenon never had the relevance it had elsewhere in the same period, *id est* in those fifty years from the last quarter of the 19th century to the first quarter of the 20th. Jews had always been linked with the liberal parties, with the monarchy and had been always assimilated in Italian society, an evidence highlighted by a large number of mixed marriages (intermarriages) between Jews and Catholics, the majoritary religion in the country. This might lead to suppose that Italy could have been an excellent immigration destination for all those Jews from Eastern Europe who were fleeing the *pogroms* or, more generally, in the great millenary framework that we can briefly label as *diaspora*. Yet this was not the case: the majority of Jewish migrants decided to settle in Germany, France, Great Britain, the former Austro-Hungarian Empire, for reasons that most probably can be traced back to economic-social reasons. Italy was still seen as a poorly industrialised country, territorially inhomogeneous, and the small size of Italian Jewry – to give indicative numbers, we speak about between 34.000 and 44.000 Jewish citizens out of a total Italian population that fluctuated between 20.000.000 and 38.000.000 units between the Unification of Italy and the First World War – made one think that processes of immigration into the country could have been faced with great difficulty by other co-religionists without resources and logistical support of significant value.²²

According to the estimates and numbers provided in 1931 – in one of the most significant censuses carried out by the Fascist regime in this sense because it was the first after the implementation of the *Falco Law* of 1930 – the number of Jews in Italy was 47,825 out of a total of approximately 41,500,000 inhabitants – more or less the 0.11%, or 1.1‰ as you like. Being estimates provided by a general census, mostly done with the timing and modalities of the past without information technology and strong systematic attention, these data should be taken with caution, yet they highlight an almost total majority of the Jewish fabric of Italian citizenship, language and social substratum: foreign Jews would in fact have been only between 11 and 12% of the total – A maximum of 5,000 units to give a purely indicative figure – among other things without pausing to specify nation of origin or profession.²³

A fact of geographical distribution must also be added. Without any real migratory movements from outside to inside the country, neither of foreigners in general nor of Jews specifically, at the turn of the two centuries, there was instead a phenomenon of internal Jewish migration, something in some ways assimilable to a broader process such as generalised urbanisation, dictated by the industrial and commercial development of the most important urban centres. While in 1840 – twenty years prior the unification of the country – there were about 87 Jewish communities all over the country, in 1931 there were only 25, albeit with considerably larger territorial districts than the

22 Cfr. T. Catalan, *Ebrei in Italia negli anni Trenta*, in *La Rassegna Mensile di Israel*, vol. 73, n. 2, May-August 2007, pp. 25-43, here 28-29. See also: M. Felstiner, *Refuge and Persecution in Italy. 1933-1945*, translated by M. Humphreys and S. Milton, in *Storia Contemporanea*, vol. 16, n. 1, February 1985, pp. 45-87, here I will not indicate the pages due to layout reasons, as I use a version of the article without page distinction. On this specific topic there are also some considerations in G. Carocci, *Storia degli ebrei in Italia. Dall'emancipazione a oggi*, Newton Compton Editori, Roma, 2005 and in R. De Felice, *Storia degli Ebrei italiani sotto il Fascismo*.

23 Cfr. T. Catalan, *Ebrei in Italia negli anni Trenta*, pp. 28-30; See also: S. Della Pergola, *Appunti sulla demografia della persecuzione antiebraica in Italia*, in *La Rassegna Mensile di Israel*, vol. 47, n. 1-6, January-June 1981, pp. 120-137, here 123-126.

previous ones.²⁴ Among the most numerous were Rome, Milan, Trieste, Turin, Florence and Livorno: central-northern cities with a high rate of urban development and industrialisation, reflecting what was said above. The majority of Jewish communities, in fact, both in the period prior to the 1930s and thereafter, always remained located in the north – the south, still scarcely industrialised at the time and without important Jewish communities, was never a privileged destination. A *unicuum*, to say so, is represented by the case of Rome, the most southern city of the ones cited but being both the most numerous and the most important Jewish community in the country, then as now, only for reasons essentially of a historical nature which can be traced back to the continuous presence of Jewish population since the days of Ancient Rome.

The Jewish Italian communities after 1933 and the arrival of foreign Jews in the country

The emigration of European Jews to other countries on the continent or even to North and South America is a rather difficult topic to deal with, especially because the characteristics of the countries of exit and of course of the countries of entry must be taken into account. Focusing on the case of immigrants and refugees of German origin, like in Mark Wischnitzier's case-study, we can divide the Jewish migration phenomenon from Germany, in the six years from 1933 to 1939, into four different waves:

1. From 1933, after Adolf Hitler rise to power, to the autumn of 1935, with the promulgation of the *Nuremberg Laws*. This period featured a huge increasing of physical violence carried out against Jews resulting in phenomenons of emigration in great number. By 1935 more than 80.000 Jewish Germans had left Germany, according to the data given by the the High Commission fo Refugees in the USA. Most of them escaped to the bordering countries: France, Switzerland, the Netherlands, Czechoslovakia, but some made it to reach also Great Britain and, overseas, a great number of countries both in North and South America or in the territories of Palestine – under British mandate.

2. From winter 1935-36 to February 1938 with a significant increase in emigration from the country, especially in the American countries even though some of them started to introduct restrictive immigration policies due to the high number of migrants.

3. Almost the entire year of 1938, during the period of the *Anschluss* and the enactment of the racial and anti-Semitic laws also in Italy. By this date almost 140.000 Jewish Germans had left the country, but still 360.000 of them remained in Germany – with a grand total of 540.000 if we consider the 180.000 in Austria.

4. From November 1938, with *Crystal Night* and the worsening socio-economic conditions of individuals of Jewish religion and origin in the country, to the beginning of the war. At the end of 1938 the estimates suggest that almost 100.000 Jews left Germany and Austria, mostly of them in the second half/last months of the year.²⁵

By the beginning of the war, according to various studies, the number of Jewish from Germany and Austria that had left the German Reich exceeded the 280.000 units. Excluding the ones who reached or were already in the Democracies of Western Europe such as France, Netherlands or Great Britain, more than 45.000 where in Palestine, more than 52.000 in the US, almost 45.000 in various countries of South America and the others all over the “non-German” world. More than 80 countries were involved in this process.²⁶

But what about Italy? Although at first the country was not considered an attractive destination for German Jewish refugees, the increase of restrictive policies towards immigrants in other countries led many of them to go beyond the criteria of the political system. Italy was indeed a fascist regime with a tendency towards totalitarianism – by the way, we can undoubtedly say that it essentially

24 *Ibidem*. See also: M. Sarfatti, *Gli ebrei nell'Italia fascista*, pp. 40-42.

25 M. Wischnitzer, *Jewish Emigration from Germany 1933-1938*, in *Jewish Social Studies*, vol. 2, n. 1, January 1940, pp. 23-44, here 23-38. See also: M. Felstiner, *Refuge and Persecution in Italy*.

26 Data available in: *Ivi*, pp. 38-39. See also: K. J. Bade, *The encyclopedia of migration and minorities in Europe: from the seventeenth century to the present*, Cambridge Uni. Press, Cambridge, 2011, pp. 65-83.

served as a model for the German one in many aspects, and Mussolini was in different occasions considered as a mentor for Hitler – but there is no doubt that in the period 1933-1938, albeit with noteworthy changes in attitude towards the Jewish question, the country and Italian politics proved to be effectively free of anti-Semitism. More than once in fact Hitler discredited Mussolini and Italian fascism for not taking the *Jewish Problem* too seriously.²⁷

Between 1933 and 1938 – in the period of *intermezzo* and crossed by Mussolini's *double-track policy* – the Italian Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the regime allowed Jewish migrants and refugees to settle in Italy without any restrictions, conditions of citizenship, religion or even visas in their passports.²⁸ The “only” condition was not to be politically active against the regime and to be silent even relating to what was happening in Germany, a demand symbolically represented a few years later, when Italy too adopted anti-Semitic policies, by the censorship placed on the controversial migrants' literature relating to Germany – the so-called *Tendenzliteratur*. And in the same time The Ministry of Internal Affairs granted the *Union of Jewish Communities of Italy* to raise money in assistance to persecuted Jews in and outside of Italy with the same model of other organizations in France, Great Britain and US. In a little amount of time more than 750.000 *Lire* were collected (around 150.000 *ReichsMarks* of the time), of which 400.000 were sent immediately to the *Palestine Fund for German Jews* and rest was used in Italy to assist the refugees.²⁹

Clearly there were several factors that led to the choice of emigrants and refugees of Jewish origin to settle in Italy, not only matters of necessity. Many artists, for example, willingly accepted the regime's relative openness to different styles and currents in art, literature and music, and were able to express themselves as long as they did not enter the sphere of political or social criticism. On the contrary, Nazism regarded contemporary movements such as expressionism, which was a decisive and important aspect of German history in the years following the First World War, seeing the artists of that current or people interested in that as degenerates, turning off many artistic ambitions of that kind. It should also be considered that the Italian mentality and cultural heritage of the country, the result of a long historical tradition of merchants, travellers and migrants themselves, allowed the country to empathise with foreign Jews without prejudices based on anti-Semitism or xenophobia. This not only depended on the general tendency to *laissez-faire* typical of early twentieth-century Italian politics, starting with the Giolitti governments, or on the glance that was turned to the historical figures of Italy's past, all more or less exiled or who had taken refuge elsewhere – from Dante Alighieri exiled from the city of Florence, and to whom he would never return, to the revolutionary Giuseppe Mazzini, exiled to France during the *Risorgimento*, passing through the poet Ugo Foscolo, who self-exiled to Switzerland and Great Britain for political reasons and felt constantly in exile from his two homelands, Zakynthos and Venice –, but also for a politically pondered choice: since the young Italian country had already experienced emigration movements for much of its very early history, especially towards the United States, Brazil and Argentina, where the most numerous Italian or Italian-origin communities overseas can still be found, protecting the interests of immigrants, whatever their origin or religion, also meant avoiding reprisals or ghettoisation phenomena for Italian communities abroad, a sort of guarantee for compatriots. Last but not least, the economic and social aspect should also be considered: Fascism's monetary and economic policies allowed large amounts of money to be transferred inside the country without any issues, the cost of living was relatively low compared to other countries, there was no shortage of job opportunities for educated workers and a lot of areas between *Trentino* and *Venezia Giulia* were – and still are – bilingual speaking both Italian and German.³⁰ In short, Italy

27 M. Michaelis, *L'influenza di Hitler sulla svolta razzista adottata da Mussolini*, pp. 257-266. See above pp. 4-6.

28 *Regio Decreto* 18th June 1931, n. 773, art. 142-152, in *Raccolta Ufficiale delle leggi e dei decreti del Regno d'Italia (Anno Domini 1931, IX)*;

29 *Accordo culturale fra il Regno d'Italia ed il Reich germanico*, Rome, 23rd November 1938.

30 M. Felstiner, *Refuge and Persecution in Italy*. See also: R. De Felice, *Storia degli ebrei italiani*, pp. 55-77 et pp. 123-132; A. Milano, *Storia degli ebrei in Italia*, Einaudi, Torino, 1963, pp. 358-409; T. Catalan, *Ebrei in Italia negli anni Trenta*, pp. 30-31.

seemed to be a good destination for German emigrants all things considered, or at least a good intermediate base for future migrations.

The data explaining and presenting the composition of the Jewish population in Italy in the period considered here can be traced back to the various censuses and demographic measurements carried out by the Italian government from 1938 until basically 1943. The main purpose of the population census was to determine the characteristics, distribution and above all the size of the population concerned, in this case the Jewish population. Such measures were taken on several occasions in Germany, in Vichy France and clearly in all areas occupied by the *Wehrmacht* during the conflict, but it can be said that the Italian government was the first to expressly concern itself not only with the size of the Jewish communities in the country, but also with the internal characteristics of these groups.³¹ It is exactly the census of August/December 1938, examined by the newly created *Directorate for Demography and Race (Direzione Generale per la Demografia e la Razza)*, that is the most precise and systematic source in understanding the numbers of the Jewish population in Italy at that time, although several flaws.

The disclosure established the presence of 58.412 residents in Italy who had at least a parent of Jewish origin. 48.032 were of Italian citizenship, the other 10.380 were foreigners resident in Italy from more than six months.³²

Religione alla nascita	Religione al censimento	Cittadinanza			Su 100	
		Italiani	Stranieri	Totale	Italiani	Stranieri
Ebraica	Ebraica	77,5	10,6	79,8	79,8	20,2
Ebraica	Altra	3,2	3,9	3,4	79,3	20,7
Ebraica	Indeterminata	0,4	0,7	0,4	72,2	27,8
Altra	Ebraica	(a)	(a)	(a)	80,0	20,0
Altra	Altra	14,7	3,4	12,6	93,3	4,7
Altra	Indeterminata	(a)	(a)	(a)	80,0	20,0
Indeterminata	Ebraica	(a)	(a)	(a)	81,8	18,2
Indeterminata	Altra	0,8	0,2	0,7	94,7	5,3
Indeterminata	Indeterminata	3,4	1,1	3,0	93,3	6,7
Totale percentuale		100,0	100,0	100,0	82,2	17,8
Numero assoluto		43.032	10.380	58.412		

Table of the 1938 census according to government's data from Sergio Della Pergola (1981)
– note the error on the “Numero assoluto” of Italian Jews: is not 43.032 but 48.032.

The problem with this revelation was – and this is something that many historians have insisted on – clearly the inaccuracy and wide fluctuation of the figures reported by the government. First of all, the main problem lays in certifying who was a “true and pure” Jew and who was not. The cases considered valid had to start, in ascertaining race, from the Jewishness or non-Jewishness of the grandparents and was based on the concept of blood, which was then passed on to the descendant, and its percentage. The characteristics were, very briefly, as follows:

a. One was Jewish if he/she was the child of both parents of Jewish descent (pure Jew) – thus with also Jewish grandparents. 100% Jewish blood.

31 S. Della Pergola, *Appunti sulla demografia della persecuzione antiebraica in Italia*, pp. 120-122.

32 Numbers given by numerous studies: De Felice, Milano, Bachi, Cavarocchi, Della Pergola et al. For a scheme on the census see *Popolazione “ebraica” secondo la religione alla nascita e al censimento, e la cittadinanza (31 dicembre 1938). Percentuali*, in S. Della Pergola, *Appunti sulla demografia della persecuzione antiebraica in Italia*, p. 125 and *Rilevazione sugli ebrei – Agosto e Dicembre 1938. Censiti secondo la cittadinanza e la “razza”*, in *Ministero degli Interni*.

b. One was Jewish if he/she was the child of a Jewish parent (pure Jew) and a mixed blood (race) parent – with one Jewish and one Italian grandparent. 75% Jewish blood.

c. One was considered mixed or unspecified Jewish if he/she was the child of a Jewish parent and an Italian parent – mixed or unspecified grandparents. 50% Jewish blood, with possible positive and negative variations.

d. One was not considered Jewish if he/she had one parent not of Jewish descent and one mixed – with one Jewish and one Italian grandparent. 25% Jewish blood, thus with a majority of Italian blood.³³

Of course, these figures took into account all those who could be considered Jews. I say ‘could’ because the main intent of the regime had an extremely functional perspective and represented the effective transition to an extremely totalitarian practice in racial first and anti-Semitic discrimination later, with the propaganda needs attached of course. The census had achieved the aim of arriving at an exact identification, characterisation and localisation of every single individual who could be connected through kinship (traced back as far as grandparents in fact) to Judaism. In this way a sort of border space was created, a line of demarcation, fear and isolation for Jews in Italy in contrast to the clear affirmation of *Aryanism* based on the German model for true Italian blooded people. As Sabatello has essentially said on the subject: «[...] the census revelation about the Jews ordered by the fascist government [was] preordained for political rather than scientific purposes». It should come as no surprise that even foreign agents of the National Socialist Party (*NSDAP-Auslandsorganisation*) were sent to Italy to spy on the activities of Jews in the country and the work of the fascist government.³⁴ As a result, it was not in the interest of the regime to actually check who was Jewish and who, instead, had converted or were children of mixed marriages between non-Jews; and therefore this allowed, in the course of time and the numerous studies conducted on the subject, to adjust the numbers in the 1938 census: the actual Jews, *id est* those who had declared to be enrolled in a community or had expressly declared themselves professing the faith, were 46.656; the other 11.756 fell into other categories, such as converts or children of mixed marriages but professing the Catholic religion.³⁵

It is evident that if one compares the data to 1931 and 1938, the balance of Jews in the country would appear to have remained roughly stable. Does this mean, therefore, that no significant phenomena of an increase in the Jewish population or migration to Italy took place? Absolutely not, although certainly less than in other countries these phenomena did occur. And if one considers the already relatively low native Jewish population, foreigners came to be a rather significant percentage out of the total. Remaining on the subject of our digression, the actual number of Jews resident in Italy, at 1938 according to the estimates of the academics, was of 46.656 Jewish registered, and of them 9.415 were foreigners. But to get to this number from 1931 to 1938 there has been various steps. It must be taken into account that from 1933 to June 1940 – when Italy entered the war on the 10th – there had been a slow but nevertheless stream of refugees arriving in Italy, and the percentage of Jews from other countries increased from 12% to 21.5% of the total.³⁶ Something that can be translated into actual numbers by looking at the various surveys that the prefects of the ninetyfour Italian provinces regularly sent to the Ministry of the Interior Affairs concerning demographic issues. To give some indicative figures – which must remain so, since passports were not yet required to clearly identify the population of the Jewish faith, who could

33 F. Sabatello, *Il censimento degli ebrei del 1938*, in *La Rassegna Mensile di Israel*, vol. 42, n. 1/2, January-February 1976, pp. 25-55, here 29-32. Really precise and clear is the scheme at p. 32. See also: R. De Felice, *Storia degli ebrei italiani*, pp. 610-620.

34 Cit. in *ivi*, p. 44.

35 Between the most recent studies F. Cavarocchi, *Il censimento degli ebrei dell'agosto 1938*, in *La Rassegna Mensile di Israel*, vol. 73, n. 2, May-August 2007, pp. 119-130, here 122-125. See also: R. De Felice, *Storia degli ebrei italiani*, pp. 6-10; F. Sabatello, *Il censimento degli ebrei del 1938*, pp. 39-43.

36 Data available in M. Sarfatti, *Gli ebrei nell'Italia fascista*, p. 33. See also T. Catalan, *Ebrei in Italia negli anni Trenta*, pp. 28-31; M. Felstiner, *Refuge and Persecution in Italy*.

therefore have easily maintained a certain degree of secrecy in this regard, and also because it was not yet something that the Italian government and border police paid attention to, it was often ignored at customs checks, given also that the exodus of German refugees, for example, compared to other European nations was minimal and far from massive –: in October 1934, there were approximately 1.129 "refugees of the Jewish faith" – 978 German citizens, 144 Polish and 7 stateless persons; in May 1936 the number of foreign citizens had reached 5.925 individuals, although many of them had already been in Italy since before Hitler's rise to power, *id est* since 1933, and could already be considered among the Jews counted in 1931: the fact remains that 1.481 of them were German citizens. The most effective numbers date back to 1938 of course: the census in fact shows that from 1933 onwards there were 2.803 emigrants and foreign refugees in Italy with German citizenship – 1.551 men and 1.215 women *ca.*, including a little less than fifty stateless and denaturalised Germans –, 279 Polish but residing in German territories, 402 Austrians who were considered Germans because they had taken refuge after the *Anschluss*, for a total of 3.484 refugees who could be considered of German origin (about 37% of foreign Jewish refugees in Italy according to scholars' estimates) – the count excludes about 640 foreigners with only a few months residence in Germany or occupied territories and does not even include many children, who entered Italy through their mothers' passports so the number can certainly be higher, not counting of course the already mentioned statistical and estimation errors considered due to the historical period and the technology available.³⁷

Of the effective 2.803 German immigrants 16 of them were considered as living in Italy since 1933, 286 since 1934, 294 since 1935, 584 since 1936, 618 since 1937 and 545 since 1938; numbers that reflect the general trend of Jewish emigrations of Germany after the rise to power of National Socialism. The migration trends of those years, as the Italian Jewish communities themselves had done and continued to do, showed a massive phenomenon of urbanisation. The Italian cities with the highest majority of foreign migrants, mostly German, were five: Milan with 1.054 individuals (37.5% of the total), Rome with 317 (11.3% of the total), Bolzano with 229 (8.3% of the total), Genoa with 198 (7.1% of the total) and Florence with 172 (6.1% of the total). Figures and displacement that more broadly reflect the trend of Italian Jewry in general: Jews in Italy in fact, as of 1938, lived more than 88% in large cities and the largest communities remained those where the influx of migrants was greatest, although some clarifications should be made. Bolzano for example, although an important destination for German Jewish migration, probably because it was the most important city in the German-speaking area of *Südtirol*, does not appear to have an overly significant Jewish community. On the contrary, several cities with a historical Jewish community such as Trieste, Venice, Livorno and Turin do not seem to have been considered as preferable destinations in migration flows, or at least not in the same percentages as other centres. Trieste, for example, had always seen major migration flows but due only to the fact that departing from its harbor there had been numerous transits to Palestine. The *HICEM* (*Hebrew Intergovernmental Committee for European Migration*) financed in fact the Italian committee of assistance in terms of sails and transports directed to Middle-East, so from 1933 to 1940 more than 120.000 Jews debarked from Trieste and almost 30.000 were of German citizenship.³⁸ Something related to that can also be seen in the Milan migration flows: more than 2.500 people had been registered in the

37 M. Felstiner, *Refuge and Persecution in Italy*. For the data: *Direzione Generale della Pubblica Sicurezza, Buste: Ebrei Stranieri 1-16*, September-December 1938, in *Archivio dello Stato, Roma*.

38 *Ibidem*. See also: F. Sabatello, *Il censimento degli ebrei del 1938*, p. 43 et 51-52. Of huge importance are also the studies conducted by Klaus Voigt on the immigrants in Italy between 1933 and 1945 and the rescue operations: K. Voigt, *Notizie statistiche sugli immigrati e profughi ebrei in Italia (1938-1945)*, in *La Raccolta Mensile di Israel, Un Decennio 1974-1984: Saggi sull'ebraismo italiano*, Israel, Roma, 1984, pp. 407-420; *Idem, Il rifugio precario. Gli esuli in Italia dal 1933 al 1945*, vol. 1, La Nuova Italia, Firenze, 1993; vol. 2, La Nuova Italia, Firenze, 1996. Concerning Trieste could be useful: G. Fano, *Comitato italiano di assistenza agli emigrati ebrei Trieste-Venezia*, in *La Rassegna Mensile di Israel*, vol. 31, n. 10-11, October-November 1965, pp. 492-530.

city between April 1933 and May 1934, but in that same year only 500 people settled, the rest of them only passed through to reach other destinations.³⁹

Map showing the most important Italian Jewish communities as at 1938
from Franco Sabatello (1976)

Already in the post-unification period, the high literacy rate and scholastic education had allowed the Jewish population in Italy to enter the various sectors of the public administration, the liberal professions, insurance companies and the already established family businesses of retail and wholesale trade, thus creating a substantial *bourgeois* profile. This is something that was also reflected in the German refugee population, which went on to occupy roughly the same working positions, and here too the 1938 census is of great help.

About 30% (47% in Milan) of the men were in industry and commerce, of whom 3% were in managerial and directorial positions. 4.3% were in the private sector, mostly marked as general employees, of which 1.4% were in the tourism sector with holiday homes, pensions or hotels – it has to be highlighted that in trade and industrial sector a good amount of the Jewish population, not only foreigners but Italians as well, was working in the textile and printing/editorial sector, starting, in continuity with the past, with private companies in Tuscany and slowly moving to the North-West between Turin, Genoa and Milan.⁴⁰ Among the liberal professions and academic roles were a large number of photographers (around 27), more than a hundred doctors, dentists and pharmacists, around thirty engineers and architects, around thirty jurists and lawyers and another thirty or so highly educated individuals divided between chemical and humanistic studies. This heterogeneous 30% also included teachers, translators, interpreters and journalists, in much smaller numbers, however. A good 17% were students and apprentices of various kinds, while more than 12% lived off personal savings and a retirement money. Among the occupational categories with the lowest percentage was agricultural work with only 1% and the 1.5% represented artists of various kinds: musicians, composers, painters and sculptors, theatre actors and directors. Famous writers, academics and intellectuals, for instance, has to be counted between the Jewish German refugee in Italy, for being themselves Jewish or for having Jewish parents or relatives in their families,

39 *Comitato di Assistenza per gli Ebrei profughi dalla Germania*, Milano, 25th May 1934.

40 Concerning the historical Jewish communities in Florence, but also with notes regarding all Tuscany and major centre like Livorno could be helpful: A. Minerbi, *La comunità ebraica di Firenze (1931-1943)*, pp. 115-222 essay in E. Collotti (ed.), *Razza e Fascismo. La persecuzione contro gli ebrei in Toscana (1938-1943)*, Carocci, Roma, 1999.

particularity establishing their exile in the Tuscan area, such as Alfred Neumann, who wrote and published two novels during his staying in Fiesole (really close to Florence), Walter Hasenclaver, Alice Berend, Rudolf Borchardt, Curt Von Faber du Faur, Kurt and Helen Wolff and Karl Wolfskehl, just to cite some of them.⁴¹

With regard to women, the percentages were very low for typically male jobs, even though there were still cases of female workers in the commercial sector, clerical workers, teachers, translators, students and professionals in various academic fields; on the other hand, more than 57% of them were housewives or were not considered to have an actual job.⁴²

The anti-Semitic legislation in Italy and the “alien Jews”

After the 7th of September 1938, in one of the many racist and anti-Semitic measures taken by the fascist government, Jewish immigrants in Italy were forced to leave the country. Any foreigner who had been resident in Italy or in the Colonial territories of Libia and Egeo since the 1st of January 1919 had six months to leave, the last permissible date was the 12th of March 1939. They were also deprived of Italian citizenship and labelled from then on as “alien Jews” (*ebrei stranieri*).⁴³ Despite the race laws Italy remained the last sanctuary for desperates: many refugees continued to enter the country in search of asylum, thanks in part to the generally lax attitude of the border police who freely allowed them to enter or pass the borders with Switzerland, France and Yugoslavia.

Between the spring and summer of 1939, of the more than 9,000 persons affected by the expulsion decree, almost 6,500 had left the country, while just over 2,300 were still in it – among them many citizens of German origin: 829 from Germany and Austria, 415 Polish and 516 stateless persons.⁴⁴ The fascist government's plan was to remove not only the foreign population, but the entire Jewish population from the country within ten years.

As said above, from 10 June 1940, the date of Italy's entry into the war, the Fascist government abandoned the ten-year expulsion plan and took preventive and internment measures against the entire foreign population still present on the territory, on the model of Germany, France and Great Britain, clearly including individuals of the Jewish religion. Fascism, however, exacerbated the persecution as the war went on and eventually it deteriorated after September 1943, when the control of the northern part of the country was taken over by the German army and with it the discourse on the “Jewish question”, thus beginning the tragic chapter of persecution, massacres and deportations in Italy as well.

Some data on the Jewish Italian communities and foreign Jews after 1945

Between the end of the Second World War and the 1960s – it is in the decade 1955-1965 that the most important studies on Judaism in Italy between the end of the 19th century and the first half of the 20th century should be placed from a historical, sociological, economic and above all demographic point of view: De Felice, Bachi, Della Pergola, Milano *et al.* –⁴⁵ the situation of the

41 Data given by M. Felstiner, *Refuge and Persecution in Italy*. Concerning the so-called German *Exilliteratur* in Italy and the works of the author cited could be of help: F. Rocchi, «Auf Wiedersehen in Florenz!» *Voci di ebrei tedeschi dall'Italia*, Firenze Uni. Press, Firenze, 2022 as part of the research project «So ist Florenz der Blumenstrauß an ihrem Herzen». *Gli intellettuali ebrei tedeschi a Firenze tra il 1933 e il 1938* of the University of Florence started in 2021. Alfred Neumann's novels are *Neuer Casar*, Milan, 1936 translated and *Kaiserreich*, Milan, 1938 translated. Both the novels were published in Italy with a translated edition in the same years they have been already published in the Netherlands: another proof of the liberal behaviour of the Italian government in matter of art and literature.

42 *Ibidem*.

43 *Regio Decreto Legge n. 1381, Provvedimenti nei confronti degli ebrei stranieri*, 7th September 1938 – XVI.

44 *Direzione Generale per la Demografia e la Razza, Buste: Ebrei Stranieri 1-20*, 20th September 1939, in *Archivio dello Stato, Rome*.

45 R. De Felice, *Storia degli ebrei italiani sotto il fascismo* (1961); R. Bachi, *La dispersione territoriale degli ebrei nel mondo, in Italia e a Roma*, in *Rassegna mensile di Israel*, vol. XXVII, n. 3-4, March-April 1962; *Idem, The*

Italian Jewish communities had changed considerably compared to the 1930s, although one fact extrapolated from Della Pergola's studies should certainly be underlined: the number of Jewish immigrants grew proportionally over time, going from 2.1% at the beginning of the 20th century, to 18.6% in 1938 and 20.5/21% in 1965. In the twenty years following the Second World War, the Jewish population in Italy never reached the same numbers as in the 1930s, but a large contribution was made by the continuous migratory movements that affected the country, such as refugees from Germany, Poland and the Soviet Union territories, or, a few years later, a strong migratory wave from Egypt following the Arab-Israeli conflict in 1956. As before the World War, migratory movements were mostly urbanised, the majority of the population settled or remained in the two largest centres, Rome and Milan, and it was precisely the latter that was the preferred destination of the foreign population: between the 1940s and the 1950s, about 57% of the Jews in the Lombard capital were born abroad.⁴⁶

Paese di nascita secondo i confini attuali	Su 100 immigrati	Su 100 ebrei in Italia	Anno di entrata in Italia	%
Europa Occidentale	4,5			
Germania, Austria	5,2		Fino al 1920	5,8
URSS, Polonia	10,2		1920-1929	6,3
Jugoslavia, Ungheria Cecoslovacchia, Romania	11,4		1930-1938	8,0
Bulgaria, Grecia, Turchia,	13,6	21,0	1939-1944	4,4
Israele.	4,4		1945-1949	16,0
Egitto	36,6		1950-1954	10,7
Siria, Libano, Iran, Iran	5,3		1955-1959	35,2
Altri paesi d'Asia e Africa	6,4		1960-1965	13,6
Nord e Sud America, Oceania	2,4			
Italia	—	79,0		
TOTALE	100,0	100,0	TOTALE	100,0

Jewish immigrant population in Italy and countries of origin as at 1965
from Della Pergola (1968)

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July 2023

Demographic Development of Italian Jewry from the Seventeenth Century. in *The Jewish Journal of Sociology*, vol. IV, n. 2, December 1962; *Idem, Progress in Demographic Research on the Jews.* in *The Jewish Journal of Sociology*, vol. VIII, n. 2, December 1966; *Idem, The World Jewish Population Study. Report of Second Annual Meeting, International Committee of the Hebrew University's Institute of Contemporary Jewry*, Jerusalem, 6th-9th of November 1967; S. Della Pergola, *Per uno studio sociologico sugli ebrei in Italia. Gli Ebrei in Italia durante il fascismo*, n. 3, in *Quaderni del Centro di Documentazione Ebraica Contemporanea*, Milano, December 1963; *Idem, Caratteristiche demografiche della minoranza ebraica in Italia*, in *Il Politico*, vol. XXXIII, n. 2, June 1968; A. Milano, *Storia degli ebrei in Italia* (1963).

46 S. Della Pergola, *La popolazione ebraica d'Italia: caratteristiche demografiche, economiche e sociali*, in *Genus*, vol. 24, n. 1/4, 1968, pp. 135-175.

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